

MIXED-MODE FLEXURE TEST FOR DELAMINATION TOUGHNESS

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ABSTRACT

In this article we introduce a mixed-mode flexure (MMF) delamination test procedure to determine the mixed-mode interlaminar fracture toughness in composites. The MMF test way combined simply mode I load and mode II load on a unidirectional composite beam with a mid-plane crack. First the mode I load was applied by placing a bar in the crack. Then the MMF test was performed by adding mode II load to the specimen. The interlaminar fracture energy G_c of unidirectional carbon-fiber/bismaleimide-resin specimens was measured. The results show that the components of G_c , G_{Im} and G_{II} , have a linear relation approximately.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination between plies is one of the main damage form and the source of failure in composite structures. Therefore, the delamination fracture of composite materials is very important and has been investigated for many years. Generally, Such delaminations initiate and propagate under the combined influence of normal and shear stresses. Tests of delamination resistance should account for the effects of combined stresses. The mixed-mode delamination testing with combined mode I and mode II loading has been conducted in several methods. For example, the cracked-lap shear (CLS), the edge-delamination tension (EDT) and the asymmetric DCB, etc. In particular, the mixed-mode bending (MMB) delamination test method proposed and modified by Reeder and Crews^[1,2] has been studied in detail and used widely in past years. Both experimental and theoretical studies by Kinloch et al^[3] has shown that the modified MMB test method is appropriate and accurate.

The advantage of the MMB test is that it covers a wide range of mode I to mode II loadings and uses a symmetrically cracked beam specimen. However, the MMB test apparatus is actually too complex, and it may cause additional effects on the experimental data. The purpose of this paper is to introduce a new mixed-mode test method

that can be easily used to measure delamination toughness in various ratios of mode I to mode II loadings.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

PURE MODE I AND MODE II TESTS

The pure mode I values for interlaminar fracture toughness G_{Ic} are usually obtained using a split unidirectional laminate loaded as a double cantilever beam (DCB), as shown in Fig. 1. The DCB tension, shown in part a of Fig. 1, is equivalent to the wedge loading in part b of Fig. 1. Because both have the same deformation, the strain energy is equal.

Fig. 1 DCB equivalent loading

By simple beam theory analysis of the specimen in Fig. 1, the mode I strain energy release rate G_I is expressed as

$$G_I = \frac{12P_1^2 a^2}{E_{11} b^2 h^3} = \frac{3E_{11} h^3 \delta^2}{16a^4} \quad (1)$$

where E_{11} is the lamina longitudinal modulus and b is the specimen width.

The pure mode II delamination test is shown in Fig. 2. These two testing types in both part a and part b of Fig. 2 are same. The mode II strain energy release rate G_I for the end-notch flexure (ENF) test is

$$G_I = \frac{9P_1^2 a^2}{4E_{11} b^2 h^3} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2 End-notch flexure test

THE MIXED-MODE TEST

The mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness can be measured using the asymmetric loading DCB test as shown in Fig. 3. For this case, $Q = P_1 - P_2$ and the load-point opening displacement δ is given by

$$\delta = \frac{4(P_1 + P_2)a^3}{E_{11}bh^3} \tag{3}$$

By applying the beam theory to this test configuration, the mixed-mode strain energy release rate G_m can be expressed as

$$G_m = \frac{3E_{11}h^3\delta^2}{16a^4} + \frac{9Q^2a^2}{4E_{11}b^2h^3} \tag{4}$$

Considering again Eqns (1) and (2), we have

$$G_m = G_I + G_{II} \tag{5}$$

The above analyses show that the mixed-mode test is formed by a combination of pure mode I and mode II tests. The mixed-mode loading in Fig. 3 represents the superposition for part a of Fig. 1 and part a of Fig. 2 loadings. Moreover, by way of the superposition for part b of Fig. 1 and part b of Fig. 2 loadings, we can obtain a new mixed-mode test as shown in Fig. 4. In order to distinguish the loading type in Fig. 3 from that in Fig. 4, we call the test in Fig. 4 the mixed-mode flexure (MMF) test. This type of test is similar to an end-notch flexure test in addition to a hinge bar placed between the end-notch faces in Fig. 4. The constant opening displacement δ caused by the hinge bar represents the mode I loading. The shear Q causing the beam flexure is the mode II loading. The mixed-mode strain energy release rate G_m remains the same expression as Eqn (4). The MMF test in Fig. 4 can be achieved easily.

Fig. 3 Asymmetric loading DCB test

Fig. 4 Mixed-mode flexure test

EXPERIMENTAL

TEST METHOD

The above-mentioned MMF test shows that the mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness can be measured by a simple testing method. The most practical MMF test is three point loading method, as shown in Fig. 5. First place the hinge bar in the crack, namely finish the mode I loading in advance. Then conduct the three-point loading MMF test. The mode II load P_I is

$$P_I = Q = \frac{Pl}{L}$$

Fig. 5 Three-point loading MMF test

The mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness is characterized by the critical strain energy release rate G_c . By the use of Eqn (5) the corresponding equation for G_c is

$$G_c = G_{I_m} + G_{II_m} \tag{6}$$

where G_{I_m} and G_{II_m} are respectively the mode I and mode II components of the mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness. The expressions for G_{I_m} and G_{II_m} are given by

$$G_{I_m} = \frac{3E_{I1}h^3\delta^2}{16a^4} \qquad G_{II_m} = \frac{9P^2a^2l^2}{4E_{I1}b^2h^3L^2} \tag{7}$$

where P is the applied load and a is the delamination length. P and a are measured at the onset of crack growth.

SPECIMEN AND TEST

A carbon-fibre/bismaleimide-resin composite was used in the present studies. A uni-directional laminate sheet was moulded using a hot press. The initial delamination was made by moulding in a double layer of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) film at one end of the sheet. The sheet was prepared from 24 plies and had a nominal thick-

ness of 2.8mm. The longitudinal modulus, E_{11} , was measured in flexure to be 130 GPa. Test specimens were cut from the laminate sheet and were 150mm long and 25 mm wide. Each specimen contained a PTFE film delamination starter which was about 30 mm long and placed at one end of the specimen between the 12th and 13th plies. The edge of the specimen was painted with a white correction liquid to make the delamination easier to see.

The tests were performed on a CSS—1101 static testing machine at room temperature. Each specimen was tested at a constant crosshead speed. During testing, the crack length was monitored with a travelling microscope and the load-displacement curve was drawn with a X—Y recorder. Many tests were performed to measure fracture toughness. The pure mode I values for delamination fracture toughness G_{Ic} were obtained using the standard DCB test method. The pure mode II values G_{IIc} were found using the standard ENF test method. The three-point loading MMF test method as shown in Fig. 5 was used to measure the mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MMF TEST RESULTS

As mentioned above, MMF tests were conducted with 24-ply unidirectional carbon-fibre/bismaleimide-resin specimens. Each specimen was 25mm wide and contained a PTFE film delamination starter at one end of the specimen. The specimen was pre-cracked to obtain initial growth length of 5 mm approximately. Before the MMF test was performing, a hinge bar was inserted in the delamination to create the mode I opening displacement δ of 1.2 mm. For the convenience of experiments the load P was symmetrically exerted at the specimen midplane. The effective length of the specimens, L, used in the MMF tests was 120 mm. Each specimen was loaded under displacement control with a rate of 0.2mm/min. The load-displacement curve was recorded, and the delamination length was measured simultaneously.

A typical diagram of the load P versus the load-point displacement Δ for the MMF test is shown in Fig. 6. The P— Δ curve is initially linear up to delamination propagation. As the delamination grows the P— Δ curve becomes nonlinear. The specimen compliance becomes more and more larger.

The recorded values for load and delamination length have been used in Eqn(7) to calculate G_{Im} and G_{IIm} . The values of G_{Im} are plotted against the corresponding values of G_{IIm} in Fig. 7 to give the failure locus for steady-state propagation of the delamination for the MMF test. The failure locus is linear approximately. The inter-laminar fracture toughness G_c varies with the G_{II}/G_I ratios. The lower and upper limit values of G_c are the pure mode I and mode II values for delamination fracture toughness G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} , respectively.

Fig. 6 P— Δ curve

Fig. 7 Mixed-mode interlaminar fracture toughness

MIXED-MODE FAILURE CRITERION

The type of failure locus is related to the property of composite. For the convenience of use, a general criterion for mixed-mode failure has been proposed as follows

$$\frac{G_{Im}}{G_{Ic}} + \left(\frac{G_{Im}}{G_{Ic}}\right)^n = 1 \quad (8)$$

where n represents the feature of mixed-mode failure. From equation (8), n can be expressed as

$$n = \frac{\ln(1 - G_{Im}/G_{Ic})}{\ln(G_{Im}/G_{Ic})}$$

The parameter n can be determined by test results of mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness. For the carbon-fibre/bismaleimide-resin composite the test results showed that $n = 0.92$. In general, equation (8) provides a good description of the failure locus and it is convenient to use.

CONCLUSION

A new mixed-mode delamination test method has been presented for a unidirectional laminate. The mixed-mode loading was created by combining the mode I loading for the DCB test with the mode II loading for the ENF test. First the mode I DCB loading was performed by placing a bar in the crack, then the mode II loading was added by the 3-point flexure test. The test apparatus has less influence on experimental results. The mixed-mode flexure (MMF) test is the more appropriate method and very simple indeed.

The delamination fracture toughness of carbon-fibre/bismaleimide-resin was measured using the MMF test method. The failure locus for G_{I_m} versus G_{II_m} was linear approximately. Experiments show that the MMF test method mentioned in this paper can be popularized in application.

REFERENCES

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